

Lexcube: Interactive Visualization and Exploration of High-Resolution Remote Sensing and Socioeconomic Data Sets

Maximilian Söchting^{1,2}, David Montero¹, and Miguel Mahecha^{1,3}

¹Remote Sensing Centre for Earth System Research, Leipzig University, Leipzig, Germany

²Image and Signal Processing Group, Leipzig University, Leipzig, Germany

³Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, UFZ, Leipzig, Germany

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Contributors¹	Maximilian Söchting (Conceptualization, Software, Data Curation), David Montero (Data Curation), Miguel Mahecha (Supervision)
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Corresponding author	Maximilian Söchting, maximilian.soechting@uni-leipzig.de

Abstract

A multitude of data streams, such as gridded climate data and biophysical parameters of land and water bodies, are utilized for monitoring various subsystems of the Earth in space and time. As sensor technology advances, the spatial and temporal resolution of these data sets continue to increase, posing a challenge in obtaining global and local insights from the data. In order to explore these large socioeconomic and multivariate remote sensing data cubes effectively, we explored different visualization approaches and extended our existing client-server software architecture Lexcube for interactive exploration and visualization of data cubes. As part of this NFDI4Earth pilot project, Lexcube has been successfully released as open-access at lexcube.org. Furthermore, new features such as animations and axis labels have been developed and a new data set from ECMWF has been added since the public release. [Lexcube.org](https://lexcube.org) has seen over 2800 users and 163,000 API

¹ Based on the CRediT Contributor Roles Taxonomy: <https://credit.niso.org/>

requests since its public release in May 2022, offering interactive visualizations for open-access to a widely interested audience. In the future, Lexcube will be extended with additional functionality, including integration into data science workflows like Jupyter notebooks, and the ability to visualize multiple cubes simultaneously. Additionally, we are aiming to open-source Lexcube in 2023, which will enable a broader audience to benefit from Lexcube's capabilities and potentially contribute to its future development.

I. Introduction

Many subsystems of the Earth are constantly monitored in space and time with a large number of different data streams, e.g. gridded climate data, biophysical parameters of the land surface, or of aquatic bodies. Since the spatial and temporal resolution of these data sets continuously rises with the development of improved sensors, global and local insights into these data sets become more difficult to obtain. In order to facilitate research processes and easily gain insights from large data cubes, we wanted to explore different approaches to interactively visualize data cubes generated from socioeconomic and multivariate remote sensing data sources. Our proposed solution was to extend our existing client-server software architecture for interactive exploration and visualization of data cubes.

State-of-the-art. There are few existing solutions that allow for interactive exploration and visualization of these large earth science data sets, posing a significant challenge for researchers seeking to extract insights from the data. The state-of-the-art for visualization includes visualization packages from scientific programming languages such as Python and R. They are feature-rich and provide comprehensive tools for creating scientific visualizations. However, they are implemented mainly for small data sets which fit into the main memory. As the data set size increases, these packages become slow to operate or even fail to generate a visualization, usually when the data set is larger than the main memory. Furthermore, these tools lack advanced interactivity and often do not allow for intuitive exploration of the data, instead having fixed bounds that can only be changed by changing the scripting code. Additionally, no available tool allows to easily visualize data as a six-sided data cube, treating the time as an equal dimension to the spatial dimensions. This NFDI4Earth pilot project focused on exploring and developing visualization approaches to address these challenges. At the beginning of the pilot project, we proposed to extend our existing client-server software architecture Lexcube for interactive exploration and visualization of data cubes.

II. Results

Figure 1: Main screen of the Lexcube software (lexcube.org).

What is the technological outcome? The main outcome of the pilot is “Lexcube”, a client-server application designed for visualizing data cubes. The server is written in Python using FastAPI, Xarray and Numpy, while the client is written in Typescript and utilizes the Three.js library. Lexcube uses a tiling approach, where tiles are pre-generated when the server is started, ensuring minimal latency when interacting with the data. This approach also ensures that Lexcube remains robust, even when many users access it, or when users are on a weak network. Benchmarking has shown that latency when interacting with Lexcube is less than a second even on older devices. Additionally, Lexcube is designed to work on desktop, laptop, and mobile devices with intuitive touch gestures, making it accessible to a wide range of users.

How to access Lexcube? Users can freely access Lexcube at lexcube.org, and images produced by the software are licensed under CC BY 4.0. Furthermore, Lexcube will be made open-source during 2023. Lexcube will also be presented as an abstract in a PICO interactive session at the EGU General Assembly 2023².

² <https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU23/EGU23-9258.html>

How to use Lexcube? When starting Lexcube, users can watch a short video tutorial. Afterwards, they are presented with a 3D cube on a black background with various UI elements at the edges and the corners of the screen. In the top right corner, it is possible to play an animation through time, open the data set menu, and open Lexcube in full screen mode. In the data set menu, users can change the current selection of the data set using three two-ended sliders, customize the current color map gradient and select a "display quality" that reduces visualization quality in favor of lower network bandwidth. In the center of the screen, users can change the perspective on the cube by dragging the cursor or using touch input on the black background. Clicking/touching and dragging on any of the cube surfaces changes the current selection of the data set, similar to dragging a 2D map in common mapping applications.

What is the innovation? The innovation of Lexcube is multifaceted. Current visualization tools do not allow for a visualization of very large data sets, while Lexcube allows to navigate large data sets such as the Earth System Data Cube (ca. 300 GB in size) interactively. Furthermore, no currently available visualization tool allows to visualize data as a six-sided 3D data cube. Additionally, Lexcube supports mobile devices natively which sets it apart from other scientific visualization libraries.

How does Lexcube help Open Science and the FAIR principles? Through the available visualization and interactive exploration of data sets on lexcube.org, the findability and accessibility of these data sets has been increased. Many users have asked for a possibility to download the data after using Lexcube. Furthermore, Lexcube integrates well into the existing data cube ecosystem by using Xarray in the server software. This effectively allows all Zarr and NetCDF data sets with longitude-latitude-time-addressing to be visualized easily, building on the existing interoperability in this domain.

III. Challenges and Gaps

What were the challenges during development? As one of the two major challenges, the open-source release, which was aimed to happen at the end of this project pilot, has been postponed. The open-source release is now targeted to happen later in 2023 due to the wish of restructuring the code base to allow a more user-friendly usage before making it public. Additionally, the feature of visualizing multiple data cubes at once has been partially worked on, but not finished for the project deadline. This is due to the implementation complexity and further refactoring necessary to bring this feature to the completion.

IV. Relevance for the community and NFDI4Earth

The Lexcube tool has made a significant impact on the community with 163,000 API requests and 2,800 users utilizing it since May 2022. Our twitter posts related to Lexcube have gathered 21 thousand video views, 774 likes and 205 retweets over three tweets. The qualitative feedback received from the community has also been positive, e.g. with Dr. Sebastian Sippel, Climate and Earth System Scientist at ETH Zurich, commenting on Twitter: “Fantastic tool! Looking forward to investigate extremes case studies [with Lexcube]!”.

Currently, the tool benefits earth system scientists who work with latitude-longitude-time data cubes, such as atmospheric scientists and meteorologists. However, there is potential for other sub-branches in the Earth System Sciences to use it for arbitrary 3D data cube visualization. For example, seismologists may visualize spectrograms across a fiber wire, resulting in a location \times time \times frequency data cube. For outreach and communication with the community, social media was utilized with Twitter posts made whenever major changes were put on lexcube.org. This helped reach many people, also during the ESA Living Planet Symposium in May 2022.

V. Future Directions

Lexcube will be further developed by Maximilian Söchting as part of his PhD project for ca. 2 more years. It will be open-sourced and be extended with new functionality. One such functionality is the ability to visualize multiple data cubes once. Additionally, we are planning to implement 3D volume visualization which would allow to look “inside” the data cubes and e.g. visualize extreme events as 3D clouds over space and time. Finally, we are looking at ways to integrate Lexcube more tightly into existing data science workflows such as Jupyter notebooks.

Once fully developed, Lexcube will allow any earth system scientist to visualize and interactively explore both public data sets and any data they curate, create or process themselves. Since Lexcube would allow for arbitrary 3D data cube visualization with the before-described features, its capabilities would not be restricted to earth sciences but could be used in any scientific field dealing with 3D data.